

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Yield potential

Ratooning ability of deepwater rice and ratoon crop herbage production

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The only crop normally grown in areas with water depths exceeding 50 cm during the cropping season is deepwater rice (DWR). Establishing a second crop after rice is difficult because supplemental water is generally not available. In recent studies of a ratoon crop under controlled shallow irrigation at IRRI, varieties differed in their ratooning ability. Ratoons produced high herbage yields in a short time.

We evaluated the ratooning ability and herbage production of 45 DWR cultivars under natural field conditions at Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, in early 1991.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. The main crop was transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing, three seedlings/hill in Jul 1990 and harvested in Jan 1991. Water depth rose to 100 cm before flowering.

Main crop straw was cut 15 cm aboveground 7 d after harvest and the crop was allowed to ratoon. No irrigation, fertilizer, or crop protection was provided. Ratooning ability and herbage yield of the ratoon crop were determined at 40 d after cutting.

Only 31 cultivars produced ratoons (see table). Most DWCT'82 entries showed very good ratooning ability; among the BKNFR82002 breeding lines only one produced ratoons. Check variety Huntra 60 showed high ratooning ability, LMN111 and PG56 produced no ratoons. (This confirmed the ratooning ability of these check cultivars under controlled irrigation at IRRI in 1990.)

Herbage yield from the ratoon crop excluding 15-cm stubble) differed. DWCT'82-1-10, DWCT'82-2-2,

Ratooning ability and herbage yield of DWR ratoon crop under natural deepwater condition. Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1991.

Cultivar	Ratoon hills (% of main crop)	Dry herbage yield 40 d after cutting	
		kg/ha	g/ratoon hill
BKNFR82002-1-2-9-5	0	0	0
BKNFR82002-1-2-9-6	0	0	0
BKNFR82002-1-2-9-7	38	98	2
BKNFR82002-1-4-2-7	0	0	0
BKNFR82002-1-4-2-8	0	0	0
BKNFR82002-2-2-3-1	0	0	0
BKNFR82002-2-5-4-5	0	0	0
DWCT'82-1-1	75	248	2
DWCT'82-1-10	91	418	3
DWCT'82-2-2	89	450	3
DWCT'82-2-10	89	426	3
DWCT'82-2-15	88	351	2
DWCT'82-5-3	90	342	2
DWCT'82-19-3	87	273	2
DWCT'82-19-9	80	292	2
DWCT'82-20-9	90	411	3
DWCT'82-20-11	81	441	3
DWCT'82-20-15	89	206	1
DWCT'82-30-5	72	241	2
DWCT'82-31-11	87	287	2
DWCT'82-34-5	73	223	2
DWCT'82-36-20	65	179	2
DWCT'82-51-11	0	0	0
DWCT'82-51-14	0	0	0
DWCT'82-59-19	89	260	2
DWCT'82-68-20	69	173	2
DWCT'82-80-7	45	96	1
DWCT'82-90-19	79	216	2
DWCT'82-121-15	87	355	3
DWCT'82-123-1	74	221	2
DWCT'82-134-2-1-0	0	0	0
HTAFR77067-16-1	0	0	0
HTAFR82023-9	0	0	0
HTAFR83019-5	39	94	2
HTAFR83019-13	24	81	2
HTAFR83025	0	0	0
HTAFR84022	43	89	1
HTAFR84045	51	99	1
LMN111'80G1C5-37-85-42	24	154	4
RGA6-5-0-0	29	105	2
SPR7295-32-1-5-3	20	169	5
SPR76136-12-FC-292-2	27	59	1
Huntra 60 (check)	71	220	2
LMN111 (check)	0	0	0
PG56 (check)	0	0	0
Mean	46	162	2
LSD (0.05)	16	111	0.70
CV (%)	24.92	53.03	32.32

DWCT'82-2-10, DWCT'82-20-9, and DWCT'82-20-11 had relatively high herbage yield; SPR7295-32-1-5-3 and LMN111 '80G1C5-37-85-42 had high herbage yield/ratoon hill but low herbage yield/unit area because of a low percentage of ratoon hills.

Average herbage yield under natural field condition was about 10 times lower than yields reported under irrigated conditions. The soil in natural deepwater

fields dried very fast and cracked within 30 d after ratooning.

When cultivars that did not produce ratoons were excluded, herbage yield from the ratoon crop was highly correlated with ratooning ability ($r = 0.875^{**}$) and herbage weight per ratoon hill ($r = 0.446^*$). These results indicate that biomass production from a ratoon rice crop in deepwater areas could provide supplemental forage for farm livestock. □